

Histogenesis of Human Fetal Kidney: A Cross-Sectional Descriptive Study in a Tertiary Care Institution in the Northeastern RegionNirmalendu Das¹, Nani Gopal Das², Rajkumari Ajita³, Chongtham Rajendra Singh⁴¹Postgraduate trainee, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India²Assistant Professor & HOD (IC), Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital³Associate professor, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India⁴Professor, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** The evaluation of fetal kidney has been subject of increased awareness for the assessment of fetal growth and development and prenatal diagnosis of renal anomalies, genetic counselling and treatment of prenatal renal disorders like Wilm's tumor, multicystic renal dysplasia, hydronephrosis.**Objective:** The aim of the study was to determine the histological development of the kidneys during the fetal period.**Materials and Methods:** The present study was carried out in the department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur. The material for the study consisted of 60 spontaneously aborted and still born human fetal specimens free from any gross congenital anomalies with gestational age between 11th to 38th weeks were collected from Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, RIMS. The kidneys were taken out from fetal specimens, fixed, processed to form slides and studied under the light microscope for histological changes of kidney with advancing age after staining with Haematoxylin and Eosin.**Results:** The capsule of kidney was made up of collagen fibres and fibroblasts at 11 weeks of gestation, which were differentiated with numerous collagen fibrils at 16 weeks and from 20 weeks onwards thick compact capsule is formed. Nephrogenic zone beneath the capsule was seen as a broad at 11 weeks of gestation which is decreased and it was almost negligible at 38 weeks of gestation. Developing glomeruli were observed in the superficial part of the cortex initially while with advancing gestational ages from 11 weeks to 38 weeks they were located in the deeper part of cortex. The cortico-medullary differentiation was appreciated from 14 weeks onwards and completed by 27 weeks, PCT and DCT were identified at 16th week of gestation. The medulla showed connective tissue and few clusters of cells at 11 weeks of gestation which were differentiated to a few collecting tubules at 14 weeks and thick and thin segments of Henle's loop were seen by 18 weeks.**Conclusion:** The present work made an initial attempt to analyze the growth pattern of kidney in human fetuses, which may prove useful in defining the fetal kidney diseases such as agenesis, hypoplasia, polycystic kidney etc., more precisely using the modern invasive or non-invasive imaging technique.**Keywords:** Crown rump length, Gestational age, Cortex, Medulla, Capsule, Glomeruli.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Kidney obtains its morphological and functional maturity through continual and mutually dependent developmental changes. It is very important to know the normal developmental anatomy of kidneys in prenatal diagnosis of renal anomalies, genetic counseling and treatment of prenatal renal disorders like Wilm's tumor, multicystic renal dysplasia and hydronephrosis etc.

Aims and Objectives-

The aim of the study was to determine the histological development of the human kidneys during the fetal period.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in the department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, and Manipur.

The material for the study consisted of 60 spontaneously aborted and still born human fetal speci-

mens with gestational age between 11th to 38th weeks were collected from Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, RIMS after taking permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee and categorized into 4 groups as Group-A (11-20 weeks), Group-B (21-27 weeks), Group- C (28-33 week), Group-D (34-38 weeks). The kidneys were taken out from fetal specimens, fixed, processed, stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin, observed under microscope and micro photographed.

Results and Observations

Group –A (11-20 weeks)

The kidney of 11-week-old fetus is found to be covered by thin capsule made up of collagen fibres and fibroblasts. In the cortex beneath the capsule there are immature, various stages of developing glomeruli are observed in the substance of the kidney interspersed with undifferentiated mesenchymal cells called nephrogenic zone. Primitive renal vesicle bends on itself giving the appearance of the comma, S' or crescent shaped body. Developing tubules within the interstitial tissue is very prominent. (Fig. 1,2)

Figure 1: Kidney at 11 weeks of gestation (H &E, 10X)

Figure 2: Cortex of the kidney at 11 weeks of gestation (H &E, 40X)

Figure 3: Medulla of the kidney at 11 weeks of gestation (H &E, 40X)

At 11 weeks medulla contains undifferentiated mesenchymal tissue containing spindle shaped cells at places arranged in groups indicating the formation of collecting tubules. (Fig. 3) At 14 weeks a zone of transition appears between cortex and medulla (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Cortex of the kidney at 14 weeks of gestation (H &E, 10X)

At 14 weeks medulla show mesenchymal tissue with some collecting tubules. (Fig. 5)

Figure 5: Medulla of the kidney at 14 weeks of gestation (H &E, 40X)

At 16 weeks many developing glomeruli are seen in the nephrogenic zone which are now compactly arranged, deeply stained, indicating the increased activity and show decrease of the interstitial tissue. Few tubules can be identified as proximal convoluted tubule and distal convoluted tubule.(Fig-6)

Figure 6: Cortex of the kidney at 16 weeks of gestation (H&E, 10X)

Medulla show mesenchymal tissue with numerous collecting tubules. (Fig-7)

Figure 7: Medulla of kidney at 16 weeks of gestation (H&E, 40X)

At 18 weeks Cortex has started differentiating into parts compacta and parts radiata. Pars compacta containing glomeruli and Bowman's capsule, proximal convoluted tubule and distal convoluted tubule with more differentiation, while pars radiata containing collecting tubules. (Fig. 8) Cone shaped pyramid is observed with apex towards the pelvis and base towards the cortex. Pelvis is lined by transitional epithelium. (Fig-9)

Figure 8: Cortex of kidney at 18 weeks of gestation (H&E, 40X)

Figure 9: Medulla of kidney at 18 weeks of gestation (H&E, 10X)

At 20 weeks Cortex show a greater number of renal corpuscles in the superficial part and proximal convoluted tubule and distal convoluted tubule in the deeper part of the cortex tubules and less amount of connective tissue. Medulla shows increased number of collecting tubules and thick and thin segment of the loop of Henle.

Group –B (21-27 weeks)

At 21 weeks of gestation periphery of the kidney still show lobulations. Well differentiated cortex

and medulla are seen. Glomeruli are well formed. Arcade system is well developed, well differentiated pars compacta or cortical labyrinth and pars radiata or medullary rays. Medulla shows a greater number of collecting tubules and thin and thick segments of loop of Henle. At 24 weeks of gestation there is reduction of amount of interstitial connective tissue and increased in number proximal convoluted tubule and distal convoluted tubule with more in number of collecting tubules with thick and thin segments of the loop of Henle. (Fig.10, 11)

Figure 10: Cortex of kidney at 24 weeks (H&E, 40X)

Figure 11: Medulla of kidney at 24 weeks (H&E, 40X)

At 27 weeks of gestation cortex appears to be very much compact by different generations of renal corpuscles. Medulla is packed with developing tubules and has reduced connective tissue.

Group – C (28-33 weeks): Well differentiated cortex with mature glomeruli is increased in number and medulla with mature, and a greater number of the collecting tubules, thick and thin segment of the loop of Henle are seen. (Fig.12)

Figure 12: Cortex of kidney at 30 weeks of gestation (H&E, 10X)

Group- D (34-38 weeks): At 34 weeks present with thick capsule with a narrow subcapsular nephrogenic zone interrupted at many places by developing tubules and renal corpuscles. The cortex shows a greater number of mature renal corpuscles (Fig.13).

Figure 13: Cortex of kidney at 34 weeks of gestation (H&E, 10X)

At 36 weeks a thin nephrogenic zone is seen. Cortical arch containing renal columns and medullary rays are well distinct.

Proximal convoluted tubules and distal convoluted tubules are distinctly seen. At 37 weeks of gesta-

tion subcapsular nephrogenic zone are very much reduced in thickness. At 38 weeks of gestation there are glomeruli which show lobulated glomerular tuft and in the deeper cortex, more mature forms of glomeruli are seen. Interstitial connective tissue is very much reduced. (Fig. 14)

Figure 14: Kidney at 38 weeks of gestation (H&E, 10X)

The medulla shows well differentiated collecting tubules and thick and thin segment of loop of Henle. Well defined pyramidal system is delineated with distinct cortex and medulla. (Fig. 15)

Figure 15: Medulla of kidney at 38 weeks of gestation (H&E, 40X)

Discussion

Present study revealed that the capsule of the kidney develops from the mesenchymatous tissue in agreement with Sharma S and Raina S1.

In agreement with the findings of Hosapatna M et al [2], Sharma S and Raina s [1], Lizardo-Daudt HM et al [3], Ram KS et al [4] this present study could reveal that kidney of 11-week-old fetus show a thick nephrogenic zone beneath the capsule containing various stages of developing glomeruli and

tubules were in the substance of the kidney interspersed with mesenchymal cells. Medulla contains mesenchymal tissue containing spindle shaped cell, arranged in groups indicating the formation of collecting tubules. Cortex and medulla did not show distinct differentiation.

In contrast to that by Almeida JR et al⁵ who has described primitive renal vesicle to form comma-shaped body and S-shaped developing glomeruli at 10 weeks of gestation, the present study shows the comma and 'S' shaped body at 11 weeks of gestation. In the present study, a zone of transition appeared between cortex and medulla at the starting of 14 weeks of gestation which is in accordance with Lizardo-Daudt HM et al [3], Sharma S and Raina S [1], Sunitha V and Rao BN [11]. In the present study, at 16 weeks the Renal capsule was well differentiated with increased in number of developing glomeruli in cortex and collecting tubules in the Medulla. The findings are similar to the studies done by Sharma S and Raina S [1], Patil S et al [9], Sunitha V and Rao BN [11], Hosapatna M et al [2], Lizardo-Daudt HM et al [3], and Tank KC et al [12]. Few tubules could be identified as PCT and DCT at 16th week, which is in agreement with studies done by Hosapatna M et al [2] and Ukey RK et al [8].

Well differentiated cortex and medulla were first observed in this study by the end of 18 weeks of gestation which is similar to Mishra S et al [6]. At 18th weeks cortex started differentiating into pars compacta containing glomeruli and Bowman's capsule, PCT and DCT while pars radiata contained collecting tubules, which is similar to the observation of Rao BN and Padmini MP²¹. The renal pelvis appears to be lined by transitional epithelium in consonance with Mishra S et al [7]. In our study at 20 weeks, cortex showed a greater number of renal corpuscles and tubules along with increased number of collecting tubules in the Medulla with distinct thick and thin segment of loop of Henle in agreement with Ukey RK et al [8], Patil S et al [9], Lizardo-Daudt HM et al [3] and Syed SA et al [10]. At 21 weeks of gestation, our study observed a well differentiated cortex and medulla similar to Sunitha V and Rao BN [11].

Our study showed a well-developed arcade system with medullary rays, cortical labyrinth at 21 weeks similar to Sharma S and Raina S [1]. In our present study, at 24 weeks there was a greater number of collecting tubules with thick and thin segment of the loop of Henle Similar to Tank KC et al [12] and Syed SA et al [10], Rao BN and Padmini MP [7], Ram KS et al [4] and Hosapatna M et al [2]. In the present study a well differentiated cortex and medulla was seen at 28-32 weeks of age groups, which is in accordance with previous observations made by Patil S et al [9], Lizardo-Daudt HM et al [3] and Hosapatna M et al [2].

In our study at 28-32 weeks of age groups, there was increased number of mature glomeruli with tubules in the cortex along with collecting tubules, thick and thin segments of the loop of Henle in the medulla with reduced interstitial tissue similar to Tank KC et al [12]. In this study at 34 weeks the cortex showed a greater number of mature renal corpuscles similar findings was observed by Patil S et al [9] at 35 weeks of gestational age.

Our finding at 37 weeks of gestation, where sub-capsular nephrogenic zone was very much reduced in thickness is similar to the result of Sunitha V and Rao BN [11]. Present study showed evidence of mesenchymatous tissue at the periphery with reduced in thickness at 38 weeks similar to Sunitha V and Rao BN [11].

In the present study the cortex of 38 weeks fetus kidney showed glomeruli with lobulated glomerular tuft in superficial and more mature forms of glomeruli in deeper cortex similar to Ljungqvist A [13]. Medulla showed well differentiated collecting tubules and thick and thin segment of loop of Henle, scanty interstitial connective tissues similar to observations of Syed SA et al [10], Tank KC et al [12], Rao BN and Padmini MP [7].

Conclusions

The present work made an initial attempt to analyze the normal histological growth pattern of kidney in human fetuses, which may prove useful in identifying any pathological changes of the kidney more precisely using the modern invasive or non-invasive imaging technique.

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